

EVIDENCE-BASED
TOXICOLOGY

Acceptance note for

TEBT-2024-0010

Submission Information Table

Submission Title	Health Impacts Associated with Community Exposure to Animal Feeding Operations: A Protocol for a Systematic Review
Submission Reference	TEBT-2024-0015 (initial submission TEBT-2024-0010)
Handling Editor	Paul Whaley ORCID 0000-0003-4021-0785
Number of Reviewers	3 peer-reviewers, 1 handling editor
Submission Type	Study Protocol ▾
Preprint DOI	Original version: https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.11110844 Updated version: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13921794
Evaluation Date	3 Apr 2025
Evaluation Stage	Peer-Review ▾
Evaluation Round	Round 2 ▾
Recommendation	Accept ▾

Editor's Summary of Reviewer Comments

Written by the Handling Editor as a summary of the key points from the peer-review process

This submission is the protocol for a planned systematic review, intended by the authors to resolve a range of issues they feel have not been addressed by previous systematic reviews on

the topic of community health impacts related to animal feeding operations. The authors and the evaluators did not fully agree on all of the choices for the planned methods. However, the evaluators did agree that the authors presented thoughtful responses to all comments and the protocol is therefore acceptable for publication without further revisions. The reviewer comments and responses contain interesting discussion of the challenges of conducting systematic reviews on this topic.

Acceptance note

This manuscript has been accepted for publication by the handling editor Paul Whaley after 3 rounds of revision in response to 1 round of editorial triage and 2 rounds of peer-review.

To the best of the editor's current knowledge, this protocol is a [Category 1 preregistration](#): because this is a systematic review of published studies, the authors may already have had access to data in a way that could allow them to anticipate the results of the review.

Per our Registered Reports policy, the manuscript following from this protocol will be accepted so long as the researchers reasonably adhere to their planned methods.

A complete record of the evaluation reports for this submission can be found at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11654905>